

DATA GOVERNANCE FRAMEWORK OF MOOC PROVIDERS IN INDONESIA

Confirmation of Sub-component testing using *Fuzzy Delphi Method*

After conducting interviews with the MOOC providers above, the researchers got answers to what sub-components were needed by MOOC providers to be used in the data governance framework. From the results obtained from the MOOC providers, the researchers conducted testing using the Fuzzy Delphi Method by calculating based on a Likert scale of 1-5, the results were obtained to be the answer to research question 1 as follows:

People and Organization

People:

Table 1. Fuzzy Delphi Calculation on People

Results	Responsibility	Stakeholders	Stewardship	Roles	Civil Society	Trust
Expert1	0	0.04619	0.01732	0.02309	0.18475	0.01155
Expert2	0	0.04619	0.04041	0.02309	0.06928	0.01155
Expert3	0	0.04619	0.01732	0.02309	0.18475	0.01155
Expert4	0	0.06928	0.01732	0.09238	0.04619	0.01155
Expert5	0	0.04619	0.04041	0.02309	0.04619	0.01155
Expert6	0	0.06928	0.01732	0.09238	0.04619	0.01155
Expert7	0	0.18475	0.01732	0.02309	0.04619	0.01155
Expert8	0	0.04619	0.04041	0.02309	0.16166	0.01155
Expert9	0	0.04619	0.01732	0.02309	0.04619	0.10392
Expert10	0	0.04619	0.01732	0.02309	0.04619	0.01155

Statistics	Responsibility	Stakeholders	Stewardship	Roles	Civil Society	Trust
Value of the item	0	0.06466	0.02425	0.03695	0.08776	0.02079
Value of the construct						0.03907
Item < 0.2	10	10	10	10	10	10
% of items < 0.2	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Average of % consensus						100
Defuzzification	0.8	0.72	0.13	0.76	0.52	0.78
Ranking	1	4	6	3	5	2
Status	Accept	Accept	Reject	Accept	Accept	Accept

Based on the ranking of the above calculations, the order of the sub-components in people is as follows:

- | | |
|-------------------|------------------|
| 1. Responsibility | 4. Stakeholders |
| 2. Trust | 5. Civil society |
| 3. Roles | |

Meanwhile, the rejected sub-component is stewardship.

Organization:

Table 2. Fuzzy Delphi Calculation on Organization

Results	Governance Metrics	Data Committee structure	Data governance office	Decision-making bodies	Employee data competencies	Methodology	Mission and vision	Ownership	Governments	Developing capabilities	Goals	KPI's	Objectives	Organization culture	Organizational maturity
Expert1	0.02309	0.04619	0.01155	0.22517	0.25403	0.25981	0.05774	0.01155	0.01155	0.2829	0.03464	0	0.04619	0.21939	0.25403
Expert2	0.02309	0.06928	0.01155	0.12124	0.09238	0.02887	0.05774	0.01155	0.01155	0.12124	0.03464	0	0.04619	0.10392	0.13856
Expert3	0.02309	0.04619	0.01155	0.2829	0.09238	0.0866	0.05774	0.01155	0.01155	0.12124	0.03464	0.23094	0.04619	0.21939	0.09238
Expert4	0.09238	0.04619	0.01155	0.1097	0.02309	0.0866	0.05774	0.01155	0.01155	0.00577	0.08083	0	0.06928	0.01155	0.02309
Expert5	0.02309	0.06928	0.04619	0.12124	0.09238	0.14434	0.05774	0.01155	0.04619	0.12124	0.03464	0.11547	0.04619	0.12702	0.09238
Expert6	0.02309	0.04619	0.01155	0.00577	0.02309	0.02887	0.05774	0.01155	0.01155	0.00577	0.08083	0	0.06928	0.12702	0.02309
Expert7	0.02309	0.04619	0.01155	0.00577	0.13856	0.14434	0.05774	0.01155	0.04619	0.22517	0.03464	0.11547	0.06928	0.12702	0.09238
Expert8	0.02309	0.06928	0.01155	0.12124	0.09238	0.14434	0.05774	0.01155	0.01155	0.12124	0.03464	0.11547	0.04619	0.12702	0.09238
Expert9	0.02309	0.06928	0.04619	0.12124	0.02309	0.02887	0.05774	0.01155	0.01155	0.00577	0.08083	0	0.06928	0.01155	0.02309
Expert10	0.09238	0.04619	0.01155	0.12124	0.09238	0.0866	0.05774	0.10392	0.01155	0.00577	0.03464	0.11547	0.04619	0.01155	0.09238

Statistics	Governance Metrics	Data Committee structure	Data governance office	Decision-making bodies	Employee data competencies	Methodology	Mission and vision	Ownership	Governments	Developing capabilities	Goals	KPI's	Objectives	Organization culture	Organizational maturity
Value of the item	0.03695	0.05543	0.01848	0.12355	0.09238	0.10392	0.05774	0.02079	0.01848	0.10161	0.0485	0.06928	0.05543	0.10854	0.09238
Value of the construct															0.0669
Item < 0.2	10	10	10	8	9	9	10	10	10	8	10	9	10	8	9
% of items < 0.2	100%	100%	100%	80%	90%	90%	100%	100%	100%	80%	100%	90%	100%	80%	90%
Average of % consensus															93
Defuzzification	0.76	0.68	0.12	0.59	0.64	0.55	0.7	0.78	0.12	0.59	0.74	0.6	0.72	0.58	0.64
Ranking	2	6	12	9	7	11	5	1	12	9	3	8	4	10	7
Status	Accept	Accept	Reject	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Reject	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept

Based on the ranking of the calculations, the order of the sub-components in organization is as follows::

1. Ownership
2. Governance metrics
3. Goals
4. Objectives
5. Vision and mission
6. Data committee structure
7. Employee data competencies
8. Organizational maturity
9. KPI's
10. Decision-making bodies

11. *Developing capabilities*

12. *Organization culture*

Meanwhile, the rejected sub-component are:

1. *Data governance office*

2. *Governments*

13. *Methodology*

Strategy

Table 3. Fuzzy Delphi Calculation on Strategy

Results	Strategic planning	Focused and tangible data strategies	Business strategy	Environment strategy	Funding strategies	Strategic alignment	Technical strategy
Expert1	0.02309	0.02309	0.05196	0.18475	0.03464	0.11547	0.09815
Expert2	0.02309	0.02309	0.34064	0.24249	0.08083	0.28868	0.01732
Expert3	0.09238	0.02309	0.06351	0.24249	0.03464	0.28868	0.306
Expert4	0.02309	0.02309	0.06351	0.04619	0.03464	0.11547	0.13279
Expert5	0.02309	0.02309	0.06351	0.16166	0.03464	0.11547	0.09815
Expert6	0.02309	0.02309	0.06351	0.04619	0.08083	0.11547	0.01732
Expert7	0.02309	0.02309	0.06351	0.16166	0.03464	0.11547	0.09815
Expert8	0.02309	0.02309	0.06351	0.16166	0.03464	0.11547	0.09815
Expert9	0.09238	0.09238	0.05196	0.04619	0.08083	0	0.01732
Expert10	0.02309	0.09238	0.06351	0.04619	0.03464	0.11547	0.09815

Statistics	Strategic planning	Focused and tangible data strategies	Business strategy	Environment strategy	Funding strategies	Strategic alignment	Technical strategy
Value of the item	0.03695	0.03695	0.08891	0.13395	0.0485	0.13856	0.09815
Value of the construct							0.08314
Item < 0.2	10	10	9	8	10	8	9
% of items < 0.2	100%	100%	90%	80%	100%	80%	90%
Average of % consensus							91
Defuzzification	0.76	0.76	0.69	0.52	0.74	0.6	0.63
Ranking	1	1	3	6	2	5	4
Status	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept

Based on the ranking of the above calculations, the order of the sub-components in the strategy is as follows:

1. *Strategic planning*
2. *Focused and tangible data strategies*
3. *Funding strategies*
4. *Business strategy*
5. *Technical strategy*
6. *Strategic alignment*
7. *Environment strategy*

Management

Table 4. Fuzzy Delphi Calculation on Management

Results	Change management	Data management	Lifecycle management	Data risk management	Data source management	Information security management	Management attributes
Expert1	0.02887	0.03464	0.21362	0.04619	0.03464	0.02309	0.20207
Expert2	0.0866	0.03464	0.13279	0.06928	0.03464	0.02309	0.14434
Expert3	0.31754	0.08083	0.27135	0.27713	0.02309	0.02309	0.25981
Expert4	0.0866	0.03464	0.01732	0.06928	0.02309	0.02309	0.02887
Expert5	0.0866	0.03464	0.13279	0.06928	0.02309	0.02309	0.14434
Expert6	0.02887	0.03464	0.01732	0.04619	0.03464	0.09238	0.02887
Expert7	0.0866	0.03464	0.09815	0.06928	0.02309	0.02309	0.0866
Expert8	0.0866	0.03464	0.13279	0.06928	0.02309	0.02309	0.14434
Expert9	0.02887	0.08083	0.01732	0.04619	0.03464	0.09238	0.02887
Expert10	0.02887	0.08083	0.13279	0.06928	0.02309	0.02309	0.02887

Statistics	Change management	Data management	Lifecycle management	Data risk management	Data source management	Information security management	Management attributes
Value of the item	0.0866	0.0485	0.11662	0.08314	0.02771	0.03695	0.1097
Value of the construct							0.07275
Item < 0.2	9	10	8	9	10	10	8
% of items < 0.2	90%	100%	80%	90%	100%	100%	80%
Average of % consensus							91
Defuzzification	0.65	0.74	0.57	0.68	0.14	0.76	0.55
Ranking	4	2	5	3	7	1	6
Status	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Reject	Accept	Accept

Based on the ranking of the above calculations, the order of the sub-components in management is as follows:

1. Information security management
2. Data management
3. Data risk management
4. Change management
5. Lifecycle management
6. Management attributes

Meanwhile, there is a sub-component that rejects data source management.

Technology

Table 5. Fuzzy Delphi calculation on Technology

Results	Metadata	Data security	Data access	Data storage	Master data	Data interoperability	Data sharing	Tools	Access control	Business intelligence	Data assets	Data availability	Data exchange	Data integration	Digital risk	Reference	Software enhancement	Artificial Intelligence (AI) System	Algorithms	Application	Business domain entities	Data collaboration
Expert1	0	0	0.02309	0.02309	0.02309	0.03464	0.06928	0.06928	0.02309	0.17321	0.03464	0	0.04619	0.03464	0.01732	0.29445	0.04619	0.03464	0.01732	0.04041	0.04041	0.07506
Expert2	0	0	0.02309	0.02309	0.02309	0.03464	0.06928	0.04619	0.02309	0.05774	0.03464	0	0.04619	0.03464	0.04041	0.00577	0.06928	0.15011	0.04041	0.01732	0.01732	0.07506
Expert3	0	0	0.02309	0.02309	0.09238	0.03464	0.27713	0.06928	0.02309	0.05774	0.03464	0	0.18475	0.08083	0.01732	0.00577	0.04619	0.08083	0.01732	0.01732	0.01732	0.32909
Expert4	0	0	0.02309	0.02309	0.02309	0.03464	0.06928	0.16166	0.02309	0.05774	0.03464	0	0.04619	0.03464	0.01732	0.00577	0.04619	0.08083	0.01732	0.01732	0.01732	0.04041
Expert5	0	0	0.02309	0.02309	0.02309	0.03464	0.06928	0.06928	0.02309	0.05774	0.03464	0	0.04619	0.03464	0.04041	0.1097	0.06928	0.08083	0.01732	0.04041	0.04041	0.07506
Expert6	0	0	0.09238	0.09238	0.02309	0.08083	0.04619	0.04619	0.02309	0.05774	0.08083	0	0.06928	0.08083	0.01732	0.00577	0.04619	0.03464	0.04041	0.01732	0.01732	0.04041
Expert7	0	0	0.02309	0.02309	0.02309	0.03464	0.06928	0.06928	0.02309	0.05774	0.03464	0	0.04619	0.03464	0.01732	0.00577	0.04619	0.03464	0.01732	0.01732	0.01732	0.07506
Expert8	0	0	0.02309	0.02309	0.02309	0.03464	0.06928	0.06928	0.02309	0.05774	0.03464	0	0.04619	0.03464	0.01732	0.1097	0.06928	0.08083	0.01732	0.01732	0.01732	0.07506
Expert9	0	0	0.09238	0.09238	0.09238	0.08083	0.04619	0.04619	0.09238	0.05774	0.08083	0	0.06928	0.08083	0.01732	0.00577	0.04619	0.03464	0.04041	0.01732	0.01732	0.04041
Expert10	0	0	0.02309	0.02309	0.02309	0.08083	0.04619	0.04619	0.09238	0.05774	0.08083	0	0.04619	0.03464	0.04041	0.1097	0.06928	0.03464	0.01732	0.04041	0.04041	0.07506
Statistics	Metadata	Data security	Data access	Data storage	Master data	Data interoperability	Data sharing	Tools	Access control	Business intelligence	Data assets	Data availability	Data exchange	Data integration	Digital risk	Reference	Software enhancement	Artificial Intelligence (AI) System	Algorithms	Application	Business domain entities	Data collaboration
Value of the item	0	0	0.03695	0.03695	0.03695	0.0485	0.08314	0.06928	0.03695	0.06929	0.0485	0	0.06466	0.0485	0.02425	0.06582	0.05543	0.06466	0.02425	0.02425	0.02425	0.09007
Value of the construct																						
Item < 0.2	10	10	10	10	10	10	9	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	9	10	10	10	10	10	9
% of items < 0.2	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	90%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	90%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	90%
Average of % consensus																						
Defuzzification	0.8	0.8	0.76	0.76	0.76	0.74	0.68	0.68	0.76	0.7	0.74	0.8	0.72	0.74	0.13	0.61	0.68	0.66	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.67
Ranking	1	1	2	2	2	3	6	6	2	5	3	1	4	3	11	10	6	8	11	11	11	7
Status	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Reject	Accept	Accept	Accept	Reject	Reject	Reject	Accept

Based on the ranking of the above calculations, the order of the sub-components in technology is as follows:

1. *Metadata*
2. *Data security*
3. *Data availability*
4. *Data protection*
5. *Data access*
6. *Data storage*
7. *Master data*
8. *Access control*
9. *Data interoperability*
10. *Data assets*
11. *Data integration*
12. *Digital audit*
13. *Data exchange*
14. *Business intelligence*
15. *Data sharing*
16. *Tools*
17. *Software enhancement*
18. *Data collaboration*
19. *Data rights*
20. *Intelligence security*
21. *Safety controllability*
22. *Artificial Intelligence (AI) system*
23. *Data cooperatives*
24. *Reference*

While there are sub-components that reject are:

1. *Digital risk*
2. *Algorithms*
3. *Application*
4. *Business domain entities*
5. *Data formats*
6. *Data marketplaces*
7. *Data services*
8. *Major technical support*

Policies / Standards / Procedures

Table 6. Delphi Fuzzy Calculation on Policies/Standards/Procedures

Results	Data quality	Law and regulations	Protection	Data principles	Guidelines	Regulatory compliance	Accountability	Privacy	Authority	Controls	Data auditability	Data consistency	Data governance level agreement	Formalization	Legal	Transparency	Confidentiality	Conformance	Data provenance	Data stewards	Empowerment value data	Ethical	
Expert1	0.02309	0.15588	0.01155	0.05774	0.03464	0.09815	0.00577	0.06928	0.0866	0.02887	0.07506	0.05196	0.13856	0.27713	0.03464	0.23671	0.03464	0.23094	0.05774	0.07506	0.01732	0.05774	
Expert2	0.02309	0.07506	0.01155	0.05774	0.03464	0.09815	0.1097	0.04619	0.0866	0.0866	0.04041	0.05196	0.02309	0.01155	0.15011	0.1097	0.03464	0.11547	0.05774	0.07506	0.04041	0.05774	
Expert3	0.09238	0.32909	0.10392	0.17321	0.03464	0.306	0.29445	0.04619	0.31754	0.31754	0.32909	0.35218	0.13856	0.27713	0.03464	0.29445	0.08083	0.23094	0.05774	0.32909	0.01732	0.05774	
Expert4	0.02309	0.07506	0.01155	0.05774	0.08083	0.09815	0.1097	0.04619	0.02887	0.02887	0.04041	0.05196	0.09238	0.12702	0.08083	0.00577	0.03464	0	0.05774	0.07506	0.01732	0.05774	
Expert5	0.02309	0.07506	0.01155	0.05774	0.03464	0.09815	0.1097	0.04619	0.0866	0.0866	0.07506	0.05196	0.09238	0.12702	0.08083	0.1097	0.03464	0.11547	0.05774	0.07506	0.04041	0.05774	
Expert6	0.09238	0.07506	0.01155	0.05774	0.08083	0.01732	0.00577	0.06928	0.02887	0.02887	0.04041	0.06351	0.02309	0.01155	0.03464	0.00577	0.08083	0	0.05774	0.04041	0.01732	0.05774	
Expert7	0.02309	0.07506	0.01155	0.05774	0.03464	0.24826	0.23671	0.04619	0.0866	0.0866	0.07506	0.05196	0.09238	0.12702	0.08083	0.1097	0.03464	0.11547	0.05774	0.07506	0.01732	0.05774	
Expert8	0.02309	0.07506	0.01155	0.05774	0.03464	0.09815	0.1097	0.04619	0.0866	0.0866	0.07506	0.05196	0.09238	0.12702	0.08083	0.1097	0.03464	0.11547	0.05774	0.07506	0.01732	0.05774	
Expert9	0.02309	0.04041	0.01155	0.05774	0.08083	0.01732	0.00577	0.06928	0.02887	0.02887	0.07506	0.05196	0.02309	0.01155	0.03464	0.00577	0.03464	0	0.05774	0.04041	0.04041	0.05774	
Statistics	Data quality	Law and regulations	Protection	Data principles	Guidelines	Regulatory compliance	Accountability	Privacy	Authority	Controls	Data auditability	Data consistency	Data governance level agreement	Formalization	Legal	Transparency	Confidentiality	Conformance	Data provenance	Data stewards	Empowerment value data	Ethical	
Value of the item	0.03695	0.10508	0.02079	0.06929	0.0485	0.11778	0.1097	0.05543	0.0866	0.0866	0.09007	0.08314	0.0739	0.11085	0.06466	0.1097	0.0485	0.09238	0.05774	0.09007	0.02425	0.05774	
Value of the construct																							
Item < 0.2	10	9	10	10	10	8	8	10	9	9	9	9	10	8	10	8	10	8	10	9	10	10	
% of items < 0.2	100%	90%	100%	100%	100%	80%	80%	100%	90%	90%	90%	90%	100%	80%	100%	80%	100%	80%	100%	90%	100%	100%	
Average of % consensus																							
Defuzzification	0.76	0.67	0.78	0.7	0.74	0.63	0.61	0.72	0.65	0.65	0.67	0.71	0.64	0.58	0.66	0.61	0.74	0.6	0.7	0.67	0.13	0.7	
Ranking	2	7	1	6	3	11	12	4	9	9	7	5	10	14	8	12	3	13	6	7	17	6	
Status	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Reject	Accept

Based on the ranking of the above calculations, the order of the sub-components in policies/standards/procedures is as follows:

- | | |
|--------------------------------|---|
| 1. <i>Protection</i> | 14. <i>Authority</i> |
| 2. <i>Data quality</i> | 15. <i>Controls</i> |
| 3. <i>Guidelines</i> | 16. <i>Data governance level agreement</i> |
| 4. <i>Confidentiality</i> | 17. <i>Regulatory compliance</i> |
| 5. <i>Privacy</i> | 18. <i>Accountability</i> |
| 6. <i>Data consistency</i> | 19. <i>Transparency</i> |
| 7. <i>Data principles</i> | 20. <i>Conformance</i> |
| 8. <i>Data provenance</i> | 21. <i>Fairness</i> |
| 9. <i>Ethical</i> | 22. <i>Formalization</i> |
| 10. <i>Law and regulations</i> | 23. <i>Openness</i> |
| 11. <i>Data auditability</i> | 24. <i>Quality assessment authentication</i> |
| 12. <i>Data stewards</i> | 25. <i>The establishment of data legitimacy</i> |
| 13. <i>Legal</i> | |

While there are sub-components that reject are:

1. *Empowerment value data*
2. *Informed consent*

Based on the ranking of the above calculations, the order of the sub-components in the *process* is as follows:

1. *Data architecture*
2. *Monitoring*
3. *Communication*
4. *Data lifecycle*
5. *Evaluation*
6. *Assessment*
7. *Training and education*
8. *Infrastructure development*
9. *Measurement*
10. *Building roadmap*
11. *Data modeling*
12. *Data traceability*
13. *Internal & external auditing*
14. *Analysis*
15. *Improved optimization*
16. *Data pre-processing*
17. *Classification*
18. *Awareness*
19. *Implementation*
20. *Organizing analytics workflow*
21. *Facilitate innovation*

While there are sub-components that reject are decision rights

Requirements

Table 8. *Fuzzy Delphi Calculation on Requirements*

Results	Trusted and clear data source	Business case	Contextual alignment	Contextual integration	Data scope	Sustaining Requirements	Deploy context Requirements	IT resources	Preparation Requirements	Private/public	Structured/unstructured
Expert1	0.03464	0.13279	0.02887	0.06351	0.02887	0.0866	0.04041	0.0866	0.01732	0.05774	0.00577
Expert2	0.03464	0.09815	0.0866	0.06351	0.0866	0.14434	0.01732	0.0866	0.01732	0.05774	0.1097
Expert3	0.1963	0.306	0.31754	0.34064	0.31754	0.25981	0.01732	0.31754	0.01732	0.05774	0.29445
Expert4	0.03464	0.01732	0.02887	0.05196	0.02887	0.02887	0.01732	0.02887	0.01732	0.05774	0.12124
Expert5	0.03464	0.09815	0.0866	0.06351	0.0866	0.14434	0.04041	0.0866	0.04041	0.05774	0.1097
Expert6	0.03464	0.01732	0.0866	0.06351	0.0866	0.02887	0.01732	0.0866	0.01732	0.05774	0.00577
Expert7	0.03464	0.09815	0.0866	0.06351	0.0866	0.0866	0.01732	0.14434	0.01732	0.05774	0.1097
Expert8	0.03464	0.09815	0.0866	0.06351	0.0866	0.14434	0.01732	0.0866	0.04041	0.05774	0.1097
Expert9	0.03464	0.01732	0.02887	0.05196	0.02887	0.02887	0.04041	0.02887	0.04041	0.05774	0.00577
Expert10	0.08083	0.09815	0.02887	0.06351	0.02887	0.0866	0.01732	0.0866	0.01732	0.05774	0.00577
Statistics	Trusted and clear data source	Business case	Contextual alignment	Contextual integration	Data scope	Sustaining Requirements	Deploy context Requirements	IT resources	Preparation Requirements	Private/public	Structured/unstructured
Value of the item	0.05542	0.09815	0.0866	0.08891	0.0866	0.10392	0.02425	0.10392	0.02425	0.05774	0.08776
Value of the construct											0.07432
Item < 0.2	10	9	9	9	9	9	10	9	10	10	9
% of items < 0.2	100%	90%	90%	90%	90%	90%	100%	90%	100%	100%	90%
Average of % consensus											93
Defuzzification	0.74	0.63	0.65	0.69	0.65	0.55	0.13	0.65	0.13	0.7	0.61
Ranking	1	5	4	3	4	7	8	4	8	2	6
Status	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Accept	Reject	Accept	Reject	Accept	Accept

Based on the ranking of the above calculations, the order of the sub-components in Requirements is as follows:

1. Trusted and clear data source
2. Private/public
3. Contextual integration
4. Contextual alignment
5. Data scope
6. IT resources
7. Business case
8. Structured/unstructured
9. Sustaining Requirements

While there are sub-components that reject are deploy context Requirements and preparation Requirements.

Other Governance

Table 9. *Fuzzy Delphi Calculation on Governance*

Results	Corporate Governance	IT Governance
Expert1	0.26558	0.03464
Expert2	0.03464	0.03464
Expert3	0.08083	0.15011
Expert4	0.03464	0.03464
Expert5	0.08083	0.08083
Expert6	0.08083	0.08083
Expert7	0.08083	0.08083
Expert8	0.08083	0.08083
Expert9	0.03464	0.03464
Expert10	0.03464	0.03464

Statistics	Corporate Governance	IT Governance
Value of the item	0.08083	0.06466
Value of the construct		0.07275
Item < 0.2	9	10
% of items < 0.2	90%	100%
Average of % consensus		95
Defuzzification	0.66	0.66
Ranking	1	1
Status	Accept	Accept

Based on the ranking of the above calculations, the order of the sub-components in other *governance* is to have the same ranking and accept, namely *corporate governance* and *IT governance*.